

OPTIMUM DESIGN OF ADHESIVE BONDING OF COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the principle of optimum design for single lap joint of composites is discussed based on the experimental and theoretical analysis. The adhesive selection, the bonding length and the thickness of the adhesive layer, the adherend design are studied also. It is shown that the strength of adhesive bonding is increased while the weight of the composites products is decreased by the optimum design so as to improve the quality of the products.

KEYWORDS: Adhesion; Composites; Optimum Design; Fiber; Shear;

1. INTRODUCTION

The majority of products of the fiber reinforced composite materials is thin-wall structure. The merits of composites may be fully played by the adhesive bonding. The adhesive bonding has following advantages: a. the joint of the same or different kinds of materials may be realized by adhesive bonding, especially for sandwich construction; b. it can lighten 20-30% weight of the products; c. the product surface joint with adhesive is smooth, fair so that the continuity of the fiber is contained and the surface pneumatic performance and fatigue strength are beneficial to improve; d. the adhesive layers have good insulation properties of electricity, heat and sound; they can be penetrated by radio wave, resistant to corrosion and good at sealing etc.; e. the bonding technique is convenient and easy to be realized by mechanization and automation.

The optimum design for composites bonding is one of the optimum designs of

composite products and with great importance. The optimum design for bonding which involve the stress analysis of joints, the selection of adhesive, the bonding theory and the bonding technical examination etc. It is a complicated synthesis of many subjects. Because the single lap joint is the simplest and is widely used, the optimum design of the single lap joint of composites is explained by the experimental results and theoretical analysis according to some assumption in this paper. The selection of the optimum parameters is discussed.

2. OPTIMUM DESIGN OF ADHESION

The optimum design for composite products bonding is complicated. There are many factors affecting its design. It is difficult to select quantitatively all optimum parameters because of the lack of quantitative description between them. In this paper we assume both of the adherends and the adhesive are elastic materials. In fact, composites have obvious nonlinear mechanics property when the tension and compression do not follow fiber direction. Since the stress-strain curves of most adhesives are nonlinear, they are treated approximately as ideal elastoplastic in stress analysis of the joints. Considering plasticity of the adhesive, the bearing capacity of bonding is enhanced. In view of the safety design, it is reasonable to assume that the adhesives are elastic materials in theoretical analysis.

2.1 Principle of Optimum Design for Bonding The purpose of optimum design for composites bonding is to make the product have minimum weight under the condition of satisfied product strength and rigidity. The wall-thickness of product is determined by the requirements of the strength and rigidity under the whole or local bearing of products. Then, subject to the condition of satisfied strength, the length of the lap joint must reduce to the shortest while the weight of adhesive layer is lightened to minimum. So the principles of optimum design for bonding are:

2.1.1 Selecting the adhesive with higher strength and extensibility, medium elastic modulus and lower contraction percentage. The thermal linear expansion coefficient of the adhesive is close to that of the adherends as fully as possible.

2.1.2 The form and length of lap joint should be designed reasonably. The stress in the adhesive layer is as uniformly distributed as possible, on the other hand, the peel and cleavage force to adhesive layer should be avoided or be reduced.

2.1.3 The adherend surface for bonding should be treated to enhance adherence strength between the adhesive layer and the adherend.

2.1.4 The reinforced fiber in joints of composites should be

arranged reasonably and the fiber surface should be treated.

2.1.5 The scientific process of spreading adhesive is used to make the thickness of the adhesive layer meet the requirement of design.

2.2 Stress Analysis of Single Lap Joint

As shown in Figure 1, when the normal stress caused by additional bending moment is not considered, the distribution of the shear stress in single lap joint may be expressed as ^[1] :

$$\tau = \frac{Pc}{2b} \left[\frac{\operatorname{ch}cx}{\operatorname{sh}^2 \frac{c}{2}} - \frac{E_2 t_2}{E_1 t_1 + E_2 t_2} \frac{\operatorname{sh}cx}{\operatorname{ch}^2 \frac{c}{2}} \right] \quad (1)$$

where t_1 , t_2 and E_1 , E_2 are thickness and elastic moduli of the adherends respectively, b is width of the specimen, and

$$c = \sqrt{\frac{2G_a}{t_a} \left(\frac{1}{E_1 t_1} + \frac{1}{E_2 t_2} \right)}$$

where G_a , t_a is shear modulus and thickness of the adhesive respectively. When we consider the normal stress caused by adherend bending, the distribution of the shear stress is as follows (assuming the materials and thickness of both adherends are the same):

$$\tau = \frac{P}{b l} \left[\frac{\beta}{8t} (1 + 3k) \operatorname{cth} \frac{\beta x}{t} + \frac{3}{4} (1 - k) \right] \quad (2)$$

where

$$\beta = \sqrt{\frac{8G_a t}{Et_a}}$$

k is coefficient of force moment, relating to the tension load, the elastic properties and thickness of the adherend and the adhesive, and the length of lap joint etc. If the adherends have not deformed before failure, that is $k=1$, formula (2) will be the same as formula (1) for adherends with the same material and thickness.

2.3 Optimum Selection of the Adhesive The formula (1) or (2) divided by average shear stress may obtain the stress concentration coefficient at the ends of the joint. For the adherend with the same material and thickness, the stress concentration coefficient may be obtained as

$$n = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{cth} \frac{cl}{2} \quad (3)$$

where

$$c = \sqrt{\frac{2G_a}{E t t_a}}$$

This shows coefficient c is related to the adhesive. According to formula (3), we must select the adhesive with lower shear modulus in order to reduce the concentration coefficient of the shear stress in the adhesive layer. Generally, the strength of material is directly proportional to elastic properties. If the selected elastic modulus of the adhesive is too low, its shear strength will be reduced. So we should select the adhesive with high strength, high extensibility and medium elastic property, and low contraction percentage. The tension-shear strength of the single lap joint of some glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) are shown in Table 1. The length of lap joint is 12.7 mm^[2].

Table 1 Tension-shear strength of some adhesives

Materials	epoxy	epoxy-nylon	epoxy-butyronitrile	epoxy-phenolic	PU	CR
τ (MPa)	20.6	44.6	27.5	20.6	10.0	2.8

This shows that it is important to select adhesive with "two high" and "one medium". This selected adhesive can give the best bearing capacity of bonding joint because it contains the largest area under its stress-strain curve. As an example epoxy-nylon adhesive is one of the best structural adhesives in which the epoxy component may enhance the shear strength, and after the nylon is added in the elastic modulus may be properly reduced but, hence, extensibility may be increased to the bigger extent. Resin is the main component of organic structural adhesive which shear modulus is not so high as required, for example, the casts of hot-cure resins only have shear moduli within the range of 0.9-1.5 (GPa). Therefore the adhesive formulated with this resin possesses lower modulus but may show good viscoelastic and nonlinear behavior after some other components are added in. For the need of present level of science and technology, the shear strength of adhesive required must reach 40-60 (MPa), the shear moduli reach 1.0-1.2 (GPa) and extensibility is bigger than 8%.

The adhesive will contract when solidifying in any way and has bigger thermal linear expansion coefficient, while the composites especially carbon and graphite fiber reinforced composites have lower thermal linear expansion coefficient. For this reason, the larger internal stress is caused in adhesive layer after composites bonded, which leads the failure of the adhesive in advance under loading. Therefore, we should select some expansible mono-

mer as the filler and add them into adhesive or expansible adhesive of CCVC-EA to control volume contraction, and as a result, the internal stress caused by adhesive contraction may be eliminated in some degrees. In the best case, CCVC-EA or expansible monomers which are added into the adhesive in proper quantity will lead to a little expansion of its volume when cured, and will fill the empty and defect existed on the surface of the adherends as well as in the adhesive itself. This can improve the adhesion behavior of the interface and enhance the bonding strength.

2.4 Design for the Adherend The design for the adherend includes three aspects: a. the selection of the elastic modulus and the thickness of the adherends; b. the surface treatment of the adherends; c. design of the joint form.

2.4.1 The selection of the elastic modulus and the thickness of adherend From formula (3) we know that the concentration coefficient of the shear stress is different for the same adhesive but different adherends. The less concentration coefficient is, the thicker and the higher elastic modulus of the adherend are, the higher average shear strength will be. Composites are designable. There are many kinds of reinforcing fiber and fabric, hence, the needed elastic modulus of the adherends may be obtained through the selection of the fiber, direction of array and the fiber content. Generally, the carbon and graphite fiber with higher elastic modulus is laid locally in the joint and the direction of the fiber is along the normal stress. Thus the elastic modulus of the adherends may be enhanced obviously. According to calculation of formula (2), if the elastic modulus increase double, the concentration coefficient of the stress is reduced by 30%, and thus the shear strength of bonding is enhanced by 43%. With respects to the content of the fiber, the elastic modulus is enhancing with the increasing of the fiber content. But at present, the interlaminar strength of composites is reducing with the increasing of the fiber content, as shown in Fig. 2. The tension-shear test of composites bonding shows that the failure of some specimen occur on the matrix between the first layer and second layer of the adherends. For adherends of composites, we must select reasonably the content of the fiber in accordance with the loading and the surface treatment of the fiber.

2.4.2 Surface treatment of the adherends Before adhesive's bonding, the surface of adherends must be treated with abrasive cloth polish or spraying sand, until the fiber is exposed. Fig. 2 shows the importance of the fiber in materials which have been treated. For example, the carbon fiber composites in which the surface of the fiber are not treated, only have interlaminar shear strength 20 MPa. For this kind of composite, it is useless even to select the strongest adhesive, because the failure occurs on

the interlamination of composites. The interlaminar shear strength of composites in which the surface of the fiber has been treated may reach 70 MPa. The surface of the carbon of the adherends should be a rough one. The effect of the surface roughness of the adherends on bonding strength is shown in Table 2. The adherends are CFRP, the adhesive is epoxy 618-3700, hot-cure [3].

Table 2 Effect of the surface roughness of the adherends on bonding strength

Surface roughness (mm)	0.03	0.3
Shear strength (MPa)	11.0	16.1
Coefficient of variance C_v (%)	7.1	9.0

2.4.3 Design for the joint form For single lap joint, the form of joint is important. If the adherend is thicker, we can adopt the form of joint as shown in Fig 3a) and d). If the adherend is thinner, we can adopt the form of joint as shown in Fig. 3c) where the fiber of higher modulus is arranged locally in the adherends, or the thickness of adherend is increased locally, so that stress concentration will be led to reduce.

In the design of the joint form, the peel and cleavage force developed in the adhesive layer should be avoided or be reduced as far as possible. According to the form of product, we can adopt the form of turning up the side or winding the fiber locally.

2.5 Selection of Bonding Length From formula (3) we know that the concentration coefficient of the stress is proportionally enhance with the increasing of joint length l , but the shear strength of bonding reducing. The relation between the shear strenght of bonding and the joint length of some group GFRP is shown in Fig. 4(the thickness of the adherend is 2.5 mm). The bearing capacity of the single lap joint is increasing with the length of joint. It tends to steady when the length reaches certain value. Therefore, there exists an optimum length of joint for the different adherends and the adhesive. The force P applied on the adherends of the single lap joint will cause an extra bend moment M_0 , because the force axis is different. Before the adherends deformed, bend moment M_0 is $Pt/2$. In fact, $M=KM_0$, where K is moment coefficient as in formula (2). The adherend is subjected simultaneously to the tension P and bend moment M at joint ends. The biggest stress is

$$\sigma = \frac{P}{bt}(1 + 3k) \quad (4)$$

When the adherends underformed, $K=1$, the stress is

$$\sigma = \frac{4P}{bt} \quad (5)$$

Then, the concentration coefficient of the stress is 4. In fact, this stress is local and the materials have a little plasticity, the concentration coefficient of the stress is 2-3. Lap tension tests of composites show that the adherends can not reach the tension strength of original material, but do not reduce to one quarter. So 2-3 is reasonable. For general composites, it is taken to 2.5 on the safety side. Considering the equilibrium between bearing forces of adherend and the adhesive layer we can get the joint length of product design as follows:

$$l = \frac{\sigma_B t}{2.5[\tau]} \quad (6)$$

where σ_B is tension failure strength of the adherend, $[\tau]$ is design value of the bonding shear strength considering the effect of the joint length

$$[\tau] = \frac{\tau_B}{n} \quad (7)$$

where τ_B is the shear strength of standard tension-shear specimen, n is the factor of length considering real joint length, generally,

$$n = \frac{0.5k_1(1+a)}{a+0.1k_2l} \quad (8)$$

where a is the lap length of standard tension-shear specimen, for which the standard of various countries is different^[4]. k_1 , k_2 are the statistics coefficient of experiment results which differ from different composites. For GFRP, we can take $k_1=k_2=1$. When l calculated from formula (6) is too long, we should reduce it by the selection of the adhesive, adherend, surface treatment, thickness of adhesive layer and form of joint etc. Otherwise, it will increase the weight of the products. The rational length of 1 lap joint is 20-30 mm.

2.6 Selection of the Thickness of the Adhesive Layer Formula (3) shows that the lower concentration coefficient of the stress is, the thicker adhesive layer is. But in fact, the tension test of resin cast shows that the higher strength, the thinner thickness of specimen. For the same as the adhesive layer, the strength of adhesive layer is enhanced with the thickness reduced. Combine both respects, there is an optimum thickness of adhesive layer for different adherends, in general, it is 0.1-0.2 mm. The effect of the thickness of adhesive layer to bonding strength is shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Effect of the thickness of adhesive layer to bonding strength

Thickness of adhesive layer t_a (mm)	0.07	0.15	0.22
Bonding strength τ (MPa)	11.9	21.1	20.7
Coefficient of variance C_v (%)	6.2	15.7	14.6

For the different form of joint and the state of subjecting load, we may design a buffer layer in adhesive layer, so as to reduce the stress concentration.

2.7 Safety Coefficient The coefficient adopted in formulae(6) and (8) is only the coefficient which be considered to the properties of adhesive bonding itself. In the design of the product, the designing stress or safety coefficient should be determined by statistics method. Otherwise the products will not be safe, at least they are not product of equal safety.

3. CONCLUSION

Researches mentioned above show that the optimum design for composites bonding is important. The optimum design of bonding is not only a task for structural designer and mechanical researcher but a synthetic problem involving many courses. The optimum design of bonding may be obtained only by combining mechanics with chemistry as well as structure with technics, and etc. For the different adherends, the product with best quality but minimum weight may be reached by selecting the optimal form of join and the optimal thickness of adhesive layer etc.

4. REFERENCES

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Figure 1

Figure 2 The Relation between the interlaminar strength σ and fiber content V_f (specimen of GFRP)

Figure 3 Improved form of single lap joint Hemf--High elastic modulus fiber

Figure 4 Relation between the shear strength and the length of bonding joint
 1-epoxy GFRP,
 2-polyster GFRP,
 3-polyster GFRP (incline lap joint, thickness is 5 mm)

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